

LINGUODIDACTIC INNOVATIONS OF THE 21ST CENTURY

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Abstract:

There is a separate field in linguistics called linguodidactics. This article about the linguodidactics, that studies the processes of language learning and teaching as well as develops methods in this century were explained.

Key words: linguodidactics, innovative teaching, effective methods, multimedia technologies, educational process.

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Linguodidactics is a science that studies the process of learning and teaching a language. It is based on a number of principles that help to effectively organize the educational process and achieve optimal results in language learning. The main purpose of teaching foreign languages is to study the language and culture of any foreign country. This goal setting determines the basic aspects of the functioning of the language education system, defining its content and forms, methods and means of mastering this content.

Linguodidactics is a scientific discipline that dates back to the 1970s. Since these years, methodological science has been striving to strengthen its theoretical foundations by implementing a truly integrative approach to defining the basic laws of the pedagogical process of teaching foreign languages in order to create an objective scientific basis for evaluating the effectiveness of teaching methods and their further improvement.

The concept of linguodidactics was introduced into scientific use by academic N.M. Shanskiy in the first half of the 20th century. As A.N.Shchukin writes, “the description, which was considered linguodidactic, included the study of the similarities and differences of languages, the analysis of the content and structure of the language being studied, the compilation of the language minima for teaching purposes and a number of other problems arising at the junction of linguistics and pedagogy.” After that N.M Shanskiy started to study the differences and similarities of languages, determining the content and structure of the language being studied, compiling language minimums in order to education and number of other issues. For example, the concept of didactics is expanding as a set of theoretical and practical issues of language teaching. Some scientists considering concepts as synonyms. N.D. Galskova believes that these concepts need to be distinguished, in her understanding, linguodidactics is a general language learning theory that develops its methodical bases, while the technique characterizes the process of learning specific language in specific conditions of its teaching (private method) or discloses the pattern of

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language learning (group of languages) outside specific conditions for its study (General technique). Linguodidactics as an integral science, it is designed to describe the mechanisms of language acquisition and the features of controlling these mechanisms in the context of educational studies. Linguodidactics is a general theory of language teaching. In the method of teaching a language as science at the present stage of development stage of development, three levels were clearly marked: methodology, linguodidactics and technology.

“Linguodidactics is a theory of language teaching, integration linguistic and didactics. Linguodidactics is a theoretical part of the methodology of teaching languages, which arose as a result of the integration of linguistics and methodology.

These days teaching foreign languages is very vital for this reason necessity for linguodidactics is increased. Linguodidactics is derived from the Latin “lingua” language and the greek “didaktikos” for teaching.

Research materials and methodology. V.M. Beldiyan first used the term didactolinguistics in a similar sense to the word linguodidactics, but later he used only the term didactolinguistics.

With the advent of multimedia resources, new opportunities have arisen for improving basic language skills, publishing student work on the Internet, searching for material for research and communicating using text, audio and video communication tools. Multimedia technologies make teaching a foreign language more effective than traditional methods. Multimedia educational technologies, such as virtual learning technology, network telecommunications, hypertext technology, allow organizing learning based on the integration of sound and video files under the control of interactive software. The didactic model of teaching a foreign language based on multimedia technologies is a system of pedagogical conditions in the unity of content-target, criteria, procedural and methodological-technological components. Their functioning is ensured by the organization of effective interaction of learning subjects in the “teacher-student” systems. For a teacher of a foreign language, multimedia natural language programs are of great interest, which can be used in language training in the following areas: work with electronic dictionaries of foreign words; the use of linguistic programs that simulate reading text in a foreign language.

The didactic properties of multimedia interactive technologies determine their didactic functions in linguistic education. Among the general didactic functions of telecommunications, E. S. Polat also includes special ones, for example, the formation of communication skills and culture of communication among partners of information exchange; promoting the cultural and humanitarian development of students on the basis of familiarization with the most

Because of many new innovations in 21st century, there are information resources of the internet are organically integrated into the educational process, helping to solve various didactic tasks in a foreign language class, for example, such as

Formation of reading skills;

Replenishment of your vocabulary of the language being studied;

Improving the ability of written speech, for example, when compiling answers to your communication partners;

Improvement of listening on the basis of original audio texts of the internet;

Acquaintance with the culture, speech etiquette, peculiarities of the speech behavior of the country of the language being studied;

Improving the ability of monologue and dialogic statements;

Formation of motivation for foreign language speech activity and knowledge of the specifics of academic writing.

One of the basic principles of linguodidactics is a communicative approach. The purpose of learning a language is to develop communication skills, that is, the ability to communicate fluently and effectively in a language. Instead of focusing on grammar and formal rules, the communicative approach focuses on the use of language in real communication situations. Linguodidactics recognizes that each student is unique and has their own individual needs and abilities in learning a language. Therefore, it is important to individualize learning, taking into account the characteristics of each student. This may include the adaptation of teaching materials, the use of various methods and approaches, as well as assessment and feedback that meet the individual needs of the student. Linguodidactics emphasizes the importance of the student's active participation in the learning process. Students should be actively involved in lessons, participate in dialogues, ask questions and put language into practice. This helps them develop self-help language skills and increase their motivation and confidence in their abilities.

Teaching one language is also called "linguodidactics" by some, the object of this field is teaching more than one language, which is different, in other words, it is language education and pedagogy. Based on this, we believe that using the combination "language learning" rather than "language teaching" reveals this process more clearly. Based on the opinion of teacher J. Jalolov, summarizing the information in modern language teaching science, we believe that it is possible to recommend the following working definition: language education means the specific study teaching monolingualism, bilingualism and multilingualism, field is understood. According to the definition, regardless of which language, under what conditions, for what purpose and how it taught, it is possible to observe commonalities in the laws of language education. For example, the development of listening comprehension, speaking, reading, and writing skills does not depend on status of the language being studied. Practice requires that these types of speech activity be studied in the mother tongue and second language too.

The conducted scientific analysis shows that new information technologies create conditions for their full implementation, radically changing the entire educational process. One of the main problems of linguodidactics is the assessment plays an important role in the educational process, as it allows teachers and students to assess progress and achievements in language learning. However, assessing language skills is a difficult task because language skills can be multifaceted and include various aspects such as grammar, vocabulary pronunciation, listening comprehension and writing. In addition, the assessment must be objective and fair to reflect the real knowledge and skills of the student. To solve this problem, teachers can use various assessment methods such as written and oral exams, tests, projects, portfolios and self-assessment.

In general, the problem of assessing language skills requires a careful approach and flexibility on the part of teachers. They should take into account the diversity of students' language skills, choose appropriate assessment methods and ensure a fair

and objective assessment that reflect the real achievements of students in language learning.

Linguodidactics recognizes that language is always used in a certain context. Therefore, it is important to teach the language in the context of real situation and tasks so that students can better understand and apply the language in real life. This may include the use of authentic materials, role-playing games, projects, and other activities that help students connect language skills to real world situations. Besides, linguodidactics emphasizes the importance of a systematic and consistent approach to language learning. Study materials and assignments should be organized in such a way that students can gradually develop their language skills and abilities. This may include the gradual introduction of new grammatical structures, the expansion of vocabulary and a gradual increase in the level of difficulty of tasks.

Linguodidactics is a science that studies the principles and methods of teaching languages. It has its own goals and objectives, basic principles and approaches. Linguodidactics plays an important role in the educational process, helping students to learn languages effectively. It is also actively used in practice, including in the development of educational materials and techniques. Trends in the development of linguodidactics are aimed at continuous improvement of teaching methods and adaptation to modern technologies. In general, linguodidactics plays an important role in the development of language education and contributes to the successful acquisition of languages by students.

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